

Program & Abstracts

7th ISAJ Symposium

India - Japan Symposium on Science and Technology for Sustainability

December 15, 2016

Main Auditorium
Embassy of India
Tokyo, Japan

In cooperation with JSPS - DST
Asia Academic Seminar 2016

Organized by

ISAJ
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

isaj.org

Kedar Mahapatra, Convener

Mahendra Kumar, Co-convener

Padinhare K. Hashim, Co-convener

ISAJ
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

The Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is a non-profit organization founded in 2008 to provide an organizational framework to promote greater interaction between Indian scientists/researchers working in Japan and the Japanese scientific community. Tsukuba Science City is ISAJ's headquarter. The Executive Body (EB) is ISAJ's governing body and is responsible for directing the affairs and determining the future of the Society. There are six different chapters in Japan (Hokkaido, Sendai, Tsukuba, Tokyo, Kyoto, and Kobe). ISAJ has organized six annual symposia at Tokyo, thirteen interactive lectures by the Tsukuba Chapter and several seminars/meetings by the Tokyo Chapter and other regional chapters. It also provides information for the advantage of the ISAJ community on the relevant news, events, funding opportunities, and every nuance of research system through homepage, newsletter, online forum, etc.

Honorary Patron:

H.E. Mr. Sujan R. Chinoy, The Ambassador of India to Japan, Tokyo

Honorary Adviser:

Dr. Purnima Rupal, Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India, Japan

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Dr. Satyaban B. Ratna, JAMSTEC, Yokohama (EB Member)

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7th ISAJ Symposium-2016 Organizing Committee

Honorary Patron: H.E. Mr. Sujan R. Chinoy, The Ambassador of India to
Japan

Honorary Advisor: Dr. Purnima Rupal, S & T Counsellor, Embassy of India,
Japan

Convener:

Dr. Kedar Mahapatra

Co-conveners:

Dr. Mahendra Kumar
Dr. Padinhare K. Hashim

Organizing Committee:

Dr. Alok Singh
Dr. Sunil Kaul
Dr. Swadhin Behera
Prof. D. Sakthi Kumar
Prof. Ruby Pawankar
Dr. Samik Ghosh
Prof. Atsushi Suzuki
Dr. Takeya Komiya
Prof. Toshio Saito
Dr. Renu Wadhwa
Dr. Manish Biyani
Dr. Asima Sultana
Dr. Baiju G. Nair
Dr. Venkata Ratnam
Dr. Rajkumar Singh
Dr. Tuba Zahra
Dr. Satyaban Bishoyi Ratna
Dr. Hirotada Moki
Dr. Venu Srinivas
Dr. Debabrata Payra
Dr. Swapnil Khodke

AMBASSADOR OF INDIA

भारत का राजदूत

(1947)

MESSAGE

I am happy to learn that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is organizing its Seventh Annual Symposium at the Indian Embassy auditorium on December 15, 2016.

The Embassy has supported the ISAJ since its inception. The Annual Symposium provides a common platform for Japanese and Indian researchers to share the results of their work and promote scientific collaboration. It is a forum that enables young Indian research scholars and students to gain a broader perspective by connecting with scientists and research institutions in Japan.

This year's theme is aptly titled - "Science and Technology for Sustainability". Both India and Japan share a vision for a sustainable future. I hope the outcome of deliberations at the Symposium will help strengthen cooperation in meeting common challenges and contribute significantly towards sustainable development.

I take this opportunity to congratulate all members of the ISAJ and the participants in the Symposium. I wish them success in their future endeavours.

(Sujan R. Chinoy)
Ambassador of India

Tokyo

09 December 2016

Embassy of India, 2-2-11 Kudan Minami, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo 102 0074

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Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

I, on behalf of the ISAJ, sincerely welcome all the delegates and guests to the 7th Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) on Science and Technology for Sustainability. Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ), a 7-year old Non-Profit Organization (NPO), was created at the end of 2008 by coming together of many Indian scientists working in Japan. Formally inaugurated by Prof. R. Chidambaram, the Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India in January 2009, in the presence of His Excellency the then Ambassador of India, it has grown into a registered NPO with its functional chapters present at Hokkaido, Sendai, Tsukuba, Tokyo, Kyoto, and Kobe. By promoting regular seminars, free discussions and networking by all of its chapters and at all levels, ISAJ has been focusing on networking among Indian scientists in Japan.

After six successful annual symposia at the Main Auditorium, Embassy of India, Japan, I am very happy to welcome you to the seventh one today with sincere thanks to the Embassy of India for their generous support and cooperation. In last six symposia, we have always tried our best to make this event interdisciplinary to allow wide participation. This year it is special and we are lucky to time it with the JSPS-DST Asian Academic Seminar 2016. Thus we have a chance to welcome several delegates from India. I truly believe that this is a unique opportunity to interact and learn beyond our specialized domains and to innovate our thoughts and research outcomes to the benefit of science and society. We very much welcome guests, especially the young researchers from India, and are looking forward to free interactions over the poster presentations by them and the young researchers working in Japan, that have been the highlight of all the earlier symposia, and it has been highly productive and enjoyable as well.

I am grateful to our guests, members and participants for their efforts to organize and participate this event. I sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium that will inspire India-Japan collaborations and friendships along with developing stronger ties in Science and Technology.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Chairman
Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Tsukuba Science City
December 10, 2016

Foreword

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we express a feeling of great honor and privilege in convening the 7th Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) entitled “India-Japan Symposium on Science and Technology for Sustainability” in cooperation with JSPS-DST Asian Academic Seminar 2016.

The global sustainability challenges facing the world today are complex and involve multiple interdependent issues such as climate change, environmental degradation, energy security, and resource depletion. A key component in responding to these issues is the development of the science and research capacity to understand the interactions among them and human systems. Increasingly, decision-makers are looking to science to provide the solutions with new technologies for sustainable economic development through a multidisciplinary approach. Keeping the above background in mind, the 7th annual symposium of ISAJ has decided to deal with the issue of sustainability this year. We are sure this symposium would enable scientists to reflect on some of these issues and to critically assess what is being prioritized, how various disciplines of science and technology can be better integrated and what this would mean for the future directions in addressing and creating innovative solutions to the sustainability challenges.

In this year's symposium, like six such events organized by the ISAJ previously, we have received enthusiastic response from the researcher community all over Japan, and also from India, especially the young scientists such as post-doctoral fellows and graduate students. In this booklet, we present 56 abstracts of the plenary talks, oral presentations and posters to be presented in the one-day event covering a wide range of disciplines such as Energy and Environment, Engineering and Material Sciences, Life Science and Biotechnology. The scientific presentations will start with the keynote address by Prof. Yoshihisa Shirayama, Executive Director, JAMSTEC. There will be 8 plenary talks by the distinguished scientists. As the last component of the symposium, we are going to have a panel discussion to explore new avenues and conceptualize strategies for taking India-Japan scientific collaborations to the next level. It is an added privilege for us to organize the symposium this year in cooperation with the JSPS-DST Asian Academic Seminar 2016. We hope the presentations and deliberations by the visiting senior scientists and young researchers from India under this program would provide impetus to the future India-Japan research collaborations in various fields of science and technology. We thankfully appreciate Prof. Atsushi Suzuki, Yokohama National University, Japan for his enthusiastic initiative in coordinating the program with us.

The Embassy of India (Tokyo) has been the core supporter of ISAJ right from its conception. The symposium would not have been possible without the generous support and guidance received from H.E. Mr. Sujan R. Chinoy, The Ambassador of India to Japan and Dr. Purnima Rupal, Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India. We are immensely thankful to EcoCycle Corporation, Forecast Ocean Plus Inc., Air India and India Tourism for coming forward to sponsor this event. On behalf of the organizing committee of this symposium, we would like to express our sincere gratitude to all the participants for the enthusiasm presenting their latest research work, and contributing to the productive interactions in the symposium.

Date: December 10, 2016

***Kedar Mahapatra, Convener
Mahendra Kumar, Co-convener
Padinhare K. Hashim, Co-convener***

7th ISAJ Symposium

India - Japan Symposium on Science and Technology for Sustainability

December 15 (Thursday), 2016

Main Auditorium, Embassy of India, Tokyo

PROGRAM

8:45 - 9:15	REGISTRATION	
9:15 - 9:20	LIGHTING OF THE LAMP	
9:20 - 9:30	Welcome Address	Sunil Kaul, Chairman, ISAJ Kedar Mahapatra, Symposium Convener
	INAUGURAL SESSION	
9:30 - 9:40	Opening Remarks	Dr. Purnima Rupal, Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India
9:40 - 9:50	Inaugural Address	H.E. Mr. Sujan R. Chinoy The Ambassador of India to Japan
9:50 - 10:10	Keynote Address	Yoshihisa Shirayama, Executive Director, JAMSTEC
10:10-10:15	Vote of Thanks	Alok Singh, Vice-Chairman, ISAJ
10:15-10:20	GROUP PHOTO	
10:20-10:40	TEA/COFFEE BREAK	

PLENARY SESSION 1 (JSPS-DST Asia Academic Seminar 2016) Chairs: Dr. Alok Singh, NIMS, Japan Atsushi Suzuki, Yokohama National University, Japan		
10:40 - 11:00	Plenary	Mamoru Mitsuishi, University of Tokyo, Japan “Bone cutting for knee joint replacement”
11:00 - 11:30	Special Plenary	Nallagundala Venkata Reddy, IIT-Hyderabad, India “Metal Forming: Mass Production to Customization”
11:30 - 11:50	<i>Introductory remarks on research activities by the visiting scientists from India</i>	
(2-3 min. each)	Indian Institute of Science: Kailas Satish Vasu (<i>Tribology, Sustainability</i>) Sanjib Sambandan (<i>Flexible Electronics</i>) Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research: Narayana Chandrabhas (<i>Chemistry, Biotechnology</i>) Indian Institute of Technology-Madras: Thalappil Pradeep (<i>Materials, Water</i>) Sundargopal Ghosh (<i>Metal-boron chemistry</i>) Indian Institute of Technology-Bombay: Chandramouli Subramaniam (<i>Sensors, Materials</i>) Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science: Suhrit Ghosh (<i>Supramolecular</i>) Indian Institute of Science Education and Research: Venkataramu Pavan Kumar Gopalapura (<i>Photonics</i>) Reji Varghese (<i>Self assembly</i>) National Chemical Laboratory (CSIR): Bhagavatula Lakshmi Vara Prasad (<i>nanotechnology</i>)	
11:50 - 12:00	Special	Shrihari Chandraghatgi, EcoCycle Corporations, Japan “Bioremediation: Cleaning ground water at industrial sites in Japan”
12:00 - 12:50	LUNCH & POSTER SESSION	
12:50 - 13:40	POSTER SESSION	

ORAL PRESENTATIONS	
Chairs: Sunil Kaul, AIST, Japan Chandrabhas Narayana, JNCASR, India	
13:40 - 13:50	Abhijit Shrotri, Hokkaido University, Japan <i>“From plants to modern chemicals: a shortcut through catalysis”</i>
13:50 - 14:00	Daisuke Kageyama, National Institute of Agrobiological Sciences, Japan <i>“Wolbachia—Intracellular microbes that manipulate reproductive systems of arthropod hosts”</i>
14:00 - 14:10	Vipin Kumar Deo, Shizuoka University, Japan <i>“Virus like particles a new tool in Nanobiotechnology”</i>
14:10 - 14:20	Naomasa Oshiro, National Institute of Health Sciences, Japan <i>“Ciguatera Fish Poisoning in Japan”</i>
14:20 - 14:30	Rumit Maini, The University of Tokyo, Japan <i>“Ribosome-mediated site-specific incorporation of dipeptides and dipeptidomimetics into proteins”</i>
14:30 - 14:40	J. V. Ratnam, JAMSTEC, Japan <i>“Heat waves and Cold waves over India”</i>
14:40 - 14:50	Adavan Kiliyankil Vipin, The University of Tokyo, Japan <i>“Cellulose nanofiber backboneed Prussian blue nanoparticles as a novel adsorbent for the elimination of radioactive cesium”</i>
PLENARY SESSION 2	
(JSPS-DST Asia Academic Seminar 2016)	
Chairs: Thalappil Pradeep and Sundargopal Ghosh	
Indian Institute of Technology-Madras, India	
14:50 - 15:10	Plenary Atsushi Suzuki, Yokohama National University, Japan <i>“High Strength Hydrogels of Physically Crosslinked Poly(vinyl alcohol) Networks”</i>
15:10 - 15:40	Special Plenary Kulkarni Giridhar Udapi Rao, Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research, India <i>“Highly Decoupled Twisted Graphene Multilayers”</i>
15:40 - 16:00	Plenary Ryuji Tamura, Tokyo University of Science, Japan <i>“Magnetism in compounds made of rare-earth icosahedra”</i>
16:00 - 16:15	TEA/COFFEE BREAK

16:15 - 16:36	<p align="center">POSTERS BY VISITING YOUNG RESEARCHERS FROM INDIA</p> <p align="center">(JSPS-DST Asia Academic Seminar 2016)</p> <p align="center">Chairs: Ryuji Tamura, Tokyo University of Science, Japan Bhagavatula Lakshmi Vara Prasad, CSIR-National Chemical Laboratory, India</p>	
		Atanu Ghosh, IIT-Madras, India, “ <i>Unusual reactivity of dithiol protected clusters in comparison to monothiol protected clusters: Studies using Ag₅₁BDT₁₉ and Ag₂₉BDT₁₂</i> ”
		Madhuri Jash, IIT-Madras, India, “ <i>Stable Gas Phase Unprotected Clusters of Noble Metals in Air from Protected Clusters in Solution</i> ”
		Papri Chakraborty, IIT-Madras, India, “ <i>Stability of Monolayer Protected Clusters towards Dissociation</i> ”
(3 min. each)		Manju Cheruvattil Koyitti, IIT-Madras, India, “ <i>Highly Luminescent Monolayer Protected Ag₅₆Se₁₃S₁₅ clusters</i> ”
		Bharath Bannur, JNCASR, Bangalore, India, “ <i>Solution Based Fabrication of a Fast Response, Broad-Band, Large Area Photodetector</i> ”
		Maku Moronshing, IIT-Bombay, India, “ <i>Thermo-diffusional behaviour of nanoparticle Colloids</i> ”
		Amrita Sikder, IACS-Kolkata, India, “ <i>H-Bond regulated distinct functional group display in vesicular assembly of unsymmetrical bola-shape π-amphiphiles</i> ”
	<p align="center">PLENARY SESSION 3</p> <p align="center">Chairs: Swadhin Behera, JAMSTEC, Japan Satish Vasu Kailas, Indian Institute of Science, India</p>	
16:36 - 16:51	Plenary	Yasumasa Miyazawa, JAMSTEC, Japan “ <i>Sustainable ocean environment monitoring scheme enhanced by ocean forecasting</i> ”
16:51 - 17:06	Plenary	Kazuyuki Inubushi, Chiba University, Japan “ <i>Sustainable paddy rice farming harmonized with greenhouse gas emission (from AMASA project in India)</i> ”
17:06 - 17:21	Plenary	Toshihiko Yada, Jichi Medical University, School of Medicine, Japan “ <i>Understanding of feeding regulation toward treatment of diabetes and obesity</i> ”

17:21 - 17:46	<p align="center">SHORT ORAL PRESENTATIONS OF SELECTED POSTERS</p> <p align="center">Chairs: Manish Biyani, JAIST, Japan Toshio Saito, Japan, Tokai University, Japan</p>
	<p>Hirotsuda Moki, PARI, National Institute of Maritime, Port and Aviation Technology, Japan <i>“The Development of a Hydrodynamic Model to Investigate the Effects of Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) Drag Force on the Current Field”</i></p>
(5 min each)	<p>Shivam Gupta, IIT, Hyderabad, India <i>“Novel Growth Factor Delivery System for Regenerative Medicine”</i></p>
	<p>Sajal AFZAL, University of Tsukuba, Japan <i>“Formulation and Characterization of Submicron O/W Emulsions Encapsulating Black Cumin Seed Oil”</i></p>
	<p>Priyanshu Bhargava, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science & Technology (AIST), Japan <i>“Honeybee propolis possess anticancer activity: bioactives, bioactivities and bioavailability”</i></p>
	<p>Devanand Tripathi, Central Institute of Plastics Engineering and Technology, India <i>“Study of mechanical mixing mechanism for sustainable polymer composite based on Polypropylene/Flyash”</i></p>
17:46 - 18:16	<p align="center">PANEL DISCUSSION</p> <p align="center"><i>What can be the next big thing to facilitate India-Japan Scientific collaborations?</i></p> <p align="center">Moderator: Swadhin Behera</p>
18:16 - 18:20	<p align="center">Concluding Session & Best Poster Awards</p> <p align="center">Chairs: Kedar Mahapatra, Mahendra Kumar, P.K. Hashim</p>
18:20 - 18:30	Tea/Coffee/Snack Break
	Cultural Program
18:30 -19:00	<p align="center">Indian Traditional Dance: <i>Odissi</i> Performance</p> <p align="center">Mayumi Fukushima and Group</p>
	Banquet
	(19:00 - 20:00)

List of poster presentations

No.	Presenter and affiliation	Presentation title
Energy and Environmental		
P1	Susant Kumar Misra, <i>DHI (India)</i>	Mathematical Modelling For Met-Ocean Design Studies At Single Point Mooring Off Hazira, Gulf Of Khambhath
P2	Hirotsada Moki, <i>National Institute of Maritime, Port and Aviation Technology</i>	The Development Of A Hydrodynamic Model To Investigate The Effects Of Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) Drag Force On The Current Field
P3	Prakhar Misra, <i>University of Tokyo</i>	Assessing Impact Of Economic Activities On Urban Air-Quality In India By Nightlight And Air Quality Remote Sensing Datasets
P4	Aggarwal R., <i>United Nations University, Tokyo</i>	A Conceptual Framework Towards Forest Fire Mitigation Practice In Part Of Indian Himalaya: A Coupled Human And Natural System
P5	Mehul Sangekar, <i>University of Tokyo</i>	Observation And Analysis Of Seafloor Resources Using Underwater Platforms
P6	Takumi Tomikawa, <i>National Institute of Health Sciences</i>	Detection Of Ciguatoxins From Finfish Caught Off The Tropical Sea
P7	Yoshihisa Hibi, <i>Tokai University</i>	Comparison Of Digestive Capability Between Toxic And Non-Toxic Puffer Fish (<i>Takifugu Rubripes</i>): An Attempt To Determine The Role Of Puffer Toxin On The Digestion Process
P8	Chauhan S.H, <i>University of Tokyo</i>	Adoption, Impact And Sustainable Management Of Medicinal Plant Cultivation For Alternative Income Generation In Tribal Communities In Gujarat
Engineering and Materials Science (including JSPS-DST Asia Seminar 2016 posters)		
P9	Devanand Tripathi, <i>CIPET, Lucknow, India</i>	Study Of Mechanical Mixing Mechanism For Sustainable Polymer Composite Based On Polypropylene/Flyash
P10	Nayuta Takemori, <i>RIKEN</i>	Local electron correlation effects on the quasiperiodic lattice
P11	Wataru Tasaki, <i>University of Tsukuba</i>	Effect Of Phase Stability On Deformation Behavior Under Tensile And Cyclic Loading In Fe-Mn-Si Shape Memory Alloy
P12	A. Ishikawa ¹ , <i>Tokyo University of Science</i>	Synthesis and magnetic properties of Au-Al-Gd approximants

P13	Srinu Gangolu, <i>National Institute for Materials Science</i>	Hot Working Flow Behavior And Processing Map Of Ti-6242S Alloy
P14	Shreya Thusoo, <i>Tokyo Institute of Technology</i>	Effects Of Interface Material On Decay Of Dynamic Response Of Free And Controlled Rocking Systems
P15	P. Seenuvasaperumal, <i>National Institute for Materials Science</i>	Effect Of High Pressure Torsion On Mechanical And Tribological Behavior Of Calcium Hexaboride Reinforced AZ31 Magnesium Composites
P16	N. Ito, <i>Tokyo University of Science</i>	Synthesis And Magnetic Properties Of The Au- Al-Yb Approximant
P17	Divya Anand, <i>University of Tokyo</i>	Flexibility and Conductivity Correlation between Polyaniline and Polystyrene-<i>block</i>-poly(2- vinylpyridine) (PS-<i>b</i>-P2VP) Based Nanocomposite
P18A	Atanu Ghosh, <i>IIT-Madras</i>	Unusual reactivity of dithiol protected clusters in comparison to monothiol protected clusters: Studies using Ag₅₁BDT19 and Ag₂₉BDT12
P19A	Madhuri Jash, <i>IIT-Madras</i>	Stable Gas Phase Unprotected Clusters of Noble Metals in Air from Protected Clusters in Solution
P20A	Papri Chakraborty, <i>IIT-Madras</i>	Stability of Monolayer Protected Clusters towards Dissociation
P21A	Manju Cheruvattil Koyitti, <i>IIT-Madras</i>	Highly Luminescent Monolayer Protected Ag₅₆Se₁₃S₁₅ clusters
P22A	Bharath Bannur, <i>JNCASR, Bangalore</i>	Solution Based Fabrication of a Fast Response, Broad-Band, Large Area Photodetector
P23A	Maku Moronshing, <i>IIT-Bombay</i>	Thermo-diffusional behaviour of nanoparticle Colloids
P24A	Amrita Sikder, <i>IACS-Kolkata</i>	H-Bond regulated distinct functional group display in vesicular assembly of unsymmetrical bola-shape π-amphiphiles
Life Sciences and Biotechnology (and miscellaneous)		
P25	A Dudani, <i>Saitama University</i>	Most Active And Responsive Site For Motilin- And Ghrelin-Induced Gastric Contractions Is Proximal Stomach In Asian Musk Shrew Stomach <i>In Vitro</i>
P26	Amrita Kumari, <i>Saitama University</i>	Synthesis Of Gb3 Polymers As Neutralizer Against Shiga Toxin O:157 Strain

P28	Sukant Garg, <i>AIST, Tsukuba</i>	NEW (Natural Efficient Economic & Welfare) Drugs For Preventive And Therapeutic Treatment Of Stress, Cancer And Neurodegenerative Diseases
P29	Rajkumar S. Kalra, <i>AIST, Tsukuba</i>	CARF Regulates Cell Proliferation In Two Directions: Stop And Go!
P30	Li Ling, <i>AIST, Tsukuba</i>	Skin Pigmentation Is A Stress Response: Molecular Evidence To The Role Of Stress Protein, Mortalin
P31	Jayarani Putri, <i>AIST, Tsukuba</i>	5'-Aza-2'-Deoxycytidine Is A Multi-Target Anticancer Drug: Bioinformatics And Experimental Evidence
P32	Shinde Harshraj, <i>University of Tokyo</i>	Studies On Sodium-Calcium Exchanger Gene (<i>NCX10</i>) In Rice In Response To Salt Stress
P33	Dudhate Ambika, <i>University of Tokyo</i>	Studies On <i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i> For Lateral Root Development And Root Skewing
P34	Sajal Afzal, <i>University of Tsukuba</i>	Formulation And Characterization Of Submicron O/W Emulsions Encapsulating Black Cumin Seed Oil
P35	Gauravkumar M. Tandel, Tokyo <i>University of Marine Science & Technology</i>	Identification And Characterization Of <i>Marsupenaeus Japonicus</i> Crustin Like Peptide (<i>Mjcrs</i>) Isoform From Kuruma Shrimp
P36	Shivam Gupta, <i>IIT- Hyderabad</i>	Novel Growth Factor Delivery System For Regenerative Medicine
P37	Parmila Kumari, Jichi <i>Medical University</i>	Central GLP-1 Receptor Agonist Promotes Insulin Release And Lowers Blood Glucose
P38	Kuniko Hanamori, <i>Tokai University</i>	Sustainability Of WASHOKU Using DNA Analysis
P39	Toshihiko Shine, <i>Shizuoka University</i>	An Introduction For Shizuoka University's Asia Bridge Program

Plenary Lectures

PL 1- 8

Bone Cutting For Knee Joint Replacement

Mamoru Mitsuishi

Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering The University of Tokyo

To replace a knee joint to the artificial joint, we have to cut the femur and tibia. In order to accelerate bone tissue regeneration into the meshed surface of the artificial joint, and consequently to enhance the adhesion force between the artificial joint and the bone surface, the damage to the bone while cutting needs to be minimalized. Bone is an anisotropic material. Therefore, the cutting phenomena are different depending on the cutting direction. High efficiency and low temperature machining is realized by the crack type cutting. On the contrary, high precision machining is realized by the flow type cutting. We are proposing 2 teeth cutting tool. Crack and flow type cutting are realized using the 1st and 2nd cutting tooth, respectively if the cutting tool is well designed. Mean value of the maximum cutting force was reduced 40% in the experiment. Furthermore, surface roughness was decreased by using the proposed cutting tool at the high efficiency cutting. Feed per tooth for the finish tooth was 100 micro meter when the feed per tooth of the proposed cutting tooth was 250 micro meter.

Relationship between surface roughness and the adhesive strength was investigated. 2 types of bone specimen from bovine were prepared in the experiment. The surface roughness was 10 and 3 micro meter, respectively. We seeded the cells (osteoblast MSC3T3-E1) on the bone surface. Biocompatible board made of Ti-6Al-4V was statically set. The surface roughness of the board was 15 micro meter. We cultivated the cells for 1 week to complete the adhesion between the biocompatible material and the bone. From the shear test, larger adhesive strength was observed when the surface roughness was 10 micro meter. It shows that it is better that the surface is not too smooth.

Metal Forming: Mass Production To Customization

N Venkata Reddy

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Societal changes impacted manufacturing including other engineering fields. Earlier industrialized economies were on mass production; however a combination of advances in technology and information is making it increasingly possible to manufacture the customized products. For mass-customization (manufacturing system shall be agile to consumers with customized products at mass production prices with equivalent or higher quality and lesser lead time), manufacturing processes have to be flexible with minimum change over time and tooling costs. Manufacturers worldwide, now attempt to grow by competing on product differentiation as much as on price. This trend leads to short product life cycles, low volume of a chosen product model, and profitability is as much dependent on the speed at which new models and products are introduced as on the control of direct cost. This trend in manufacturing sector led to development of flexible manufacturing technologies, and particularly in the area of machining to changeover between different products with the help of fully automated systems. However, developments in the area of flexible forming have not kept pace with machining mainly because of the requirement of component specific tooling in many of the operations. This presentation is going to cover some of the attempts made to develop flexible forming processes with emphasis on incremental sheet metal forming.

High Strength Hydrogels Of Physically Crosslinked Poly(Vinyl Alcohol) Networks

Atsushi Suzuki

*Graduate School of Environment and Information Sciences,
Yokohama National University, asuzuki@ynu.ac.jp*

Physically crosslinked poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) gels are versatile biomaterials and offer the advantages of excellent mechanical properties and water retention. Among the preparation methods, the cryogelation by freeze-thawing (FT) treatment and the dehydration by cast-drying (CD) treatment of the aqueous PVA solutions have been extensively studied for biomedical and industrial applications. Although their swelling and mechanical properties can be enhanced to some extent by adjusting the gelation conditions, achieving both high strength and high water absorbance is not possible via the existing preparation methods. Therefore, further improvements of the methods to control the nano- and micro-scale structures are desired.

Recently, superior swelling and mechanical properties were developed by introducing artificial processes to control the polymer networks of FT or CD gels on multiple length scales. In contrast to conventional fabrication methods of FT and CD gels, an oriented fibril network and an accumulated interface can be formed in FT and CD gels by employing unidirectional freezing and lamination methods, respectively. The anisotropic nature of these networks leads to enhanced mechanical performance, which has not been observed in gels produced by conventional single-step processes.

This talk deals with the recent advances in the preparation techniques of physical PVA hydrogels with higher swelling and mechanical performances.

Acknowledgment

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Highly Decoupled Twisted Graphene Multilayers

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The extraordinary properties of graphene are truly observable when it is suspended, being free from any substrate influence. In this presentation, a new type of multilayer graphene system will be described wherein each layer is turbostratically decoupled, resembling the suspended graphene, while maintaining high degree of 2D crystallinity. Such defect-free graphene multilayers have been made reproducibly over large areas in our laboratory by a simple synthetic method not involving hydrogen. The decoupled nature of the graphene layers is evidenced using Raman measurements, XRD, TEM and SAED. The c-axis resistance values are found to be three orders higher compared to conventional multilayers. These multistacks exhibit interesting metal-insulator transitions in their transport and photoconductive behaviors. The high 2D crystallinity observed along with the decoupled nature should accredit the observed graphene species as a close cousin of suspended graphene.

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Magnetism In Compounds Made Of Rare-Earth Icosahedra

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The discovery of the icosahedral quasicrystals (QCs) [1] has shed light on the existences of closely-related crystals called “approximants”, which are made of the same icosahedral clusters found in QCs. Tsai-type approximants containing rare-earth (R) icosahedra are of particular interest in view of their magnetism since they provide unique localized spin systems, i.e., periodic arrangement of R spin icosahedra. As a result of extensive investigations on a number of binary and ternary Tsai-type approximants, various magnetic orders including antiferromagnetic, ferromagnetic and spin-glass transitions have been observed and the origin of such different behaviours has now become an interesting issue. Moreover, recently, a composition-driven spin glass to ferromagnetic transition has been observed in Au-Al-Gd [2], which indicates that the magnetic order of approximants is governed by the oscillating nature of the RKKY interaction between localized spins. This observation will give us a hint on how to tune the magnetic order of approximants as well as QCs. In this talk, we will give an overview of the magnetism in the approximants composed of R spin icosahedra and discuss the behaviours of spin icosahedra embedded in a bcc lattice, in terms of the RKKY interaction, local anisotropy and frustration. We will also show that the Tsai-type approximants can become a potential candidate for a new frustrate system since it contains R icosahedra composed of almost regular triangles.

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PL6

Sustainable Ocean Environment Monitoring Scheme Enhanced By Ocean Forecasting

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Numerical ocean current forecast provides useful information for human marine activity including shipping, fishery, marine leisure, and ocean drilling. In Japan, the use of ocean current forecast actually contributes to ship routing that allows effective reduction of fuel usage and CO₂ emission. The ocean forecast absolutely requires ocean observation data used for estimation of realistic oceanic conditions in real-time basis. Remote sensing data from space including altimetry data obtained by an Indian satellite Saral/Altika are most crucial for the real-time operation. Recently we have been developing a sustainable field ocean monitoring scheme compensating the remote sensing through utilization of a feedback mechanism between users and forecast providers. This scheme is based on assimilation of observation data provided from users themselves into ocean forecasting models, leading to enhancement of observation activity motivated by use of improved forecast information. I show typical examples using bio- and ship- logging data assimilation.

Sustainable Paddy Rice Farming Harmonized With Greenhouse Gas Emission/From AMASA Project In India

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South Asian economy has been traditionally based on agriculture, and our estimations suggest a large fraction, up to about 10% of global total of methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) are emitted from this region. India is also a key player in the region emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) by fossil fuel consumption, 3rd largest in the world at about 555 megatons of carbon, which is about 90% of that from South Asia. CH₄ and N₂O have about 30 and 300 times, respectively, more potential for global warming in mole basis on 100 years integration time. CH₄ also plays a role in air pollution chemistry, which has been rising in the South Asian cities.

We have initiated a project, Atmospheric Methane from Agriculture in South Asia (AMASA), funded by the Ministry of Environment, Japan to study methane emissions from South Asia. Most of methane emissions from Asia are attributable to ruminant animals and rice fields. We are now collaborating with scientists and farmers in India and Bangladesh to carry out in-situ measurements and working towards improving the emission estimates by using atmospheric CH₄ concentrations measured from the JAXA's GOSAT, ground-based data and chemistry-transport models.

Our final goal is to come up with emission mitigation proposals for CH₄ from the rice fields. Experiments are being conducted in rice fields managed by the TRRI, Aduthurai for intermittent draining of water, fertilizer management and rice cultivars for CH₄ emission reduction potential and yields. This study and other experiences with N₂O emissions from various types of agricultural fields will provide us guidance on sustainable food production and climate change mitigation.

Understanding of Feeding Regulation Toward Treatment of Diabetes and Obesity

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Fine regulation of food intake is essential for healthy life. Food intake is regulated by the interaction between the peripheral nutritional/hormonal factors and the central feeding center in the hypothalamus. Under fasted states, lowering blood glucose and a rise in gastric hormone ghrelin activate the hypothalamic orexigenic Neuropeptide Y (NPY) neurons, which drives appetite through downstream neurocircuit including inhibition of anorexigenic oxytocin neurons. After food ingestion, rises in blood glucose, intestinal hormone Glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and adipocyte hormone leptin activate anorexigenic Proopiomelanocortine (POMC) neurons, which produces satiety via downstream neurocircuit including activation of oxytocin neurons. Oxytocin neurons are also directly activated by GLP-1 and by fed states.

Thus, feeding is reciprocally regulated by these orexigenic and anorexigenic systems, composed of the neurons receiving nutrients and hormones representing body's metabolic condition. The balance between these systems maintains homeostatic regulation of feeding and body weight. However, modern life with easy access to abundance of sweet, fatty and/or hedonic foods destruct the balance, thereby inducing overeating and obesity, which secondarily lead to type-2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome. In high fat diet-induced obese mice, oxytocin expression in the hypothalamus is impaired, and injection of oxytocin into the brain ameliorates obesity. Surprisingly, even peripheral injection of oxytocin corrects obesity, diabetes and metabolic syndrome. This may provide a novel treatment of obesity, the disease becoming pandemic world wide including India and Japan, for which no safe and effective medicines are currently available.

Special Talk

Bioremediation: Cleaning Ground Water At Industrial Sites In Japan

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Groundwater is a lifeline for billions world-wide. Yet agricultural and industrial activities have been contaminating it with toxic organic chemicals and heavy metals. Bioremediation has been found cost effective *in-situ* remedial alternative for cleaning these carcinogens. The paper covers groundbreaking innovations at EcoCycle Corporations with specific case studies of cleaning large former industrial sites in Japan.

Oral Presentations

01 – 07

O-1

From Plants To Modern Chemicals: A Shortcut Through Catalysis

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Transportation fuels and commodity chemical are produced from crude oil, a dwindling and damaging resource, which must be replaced in the near future. To attain this goal, we are using readily available plant biomass as an alternative resource to crude oil. A major constituent of plant biomass is cellulose, which is a linear polymer of glucose that serves as an intermediate between biomass and useful chemicals.¹ However, breaking down cellulose to produce glucose is a major challenge as cellulose is indigestible and unreactive. Naturally, only enzymes produced by bacteria can breakdown cellulose in a slow process, which is not suitable for industrial application. To overcome this problem, we have developed an inexpensive and durable carbon catalyst that can breakdown cellulose to yield glucose in high yield after short reaction time.² The catalyst mimics enzymes by grabbing the cellulose molecule through hydrophobic adsorption and then breaking the glycosidic linkage between glucose monomers. The carbon catalyst itself can be made from plant biomass by oxidation in the presence of air, which reduces cost and minimizes waste production. We have also developed a model reactor system to demonstrate that the process is feasible for industrial application. We believe that this process will reduce our dependence on fossil fuels and provide a sustainable alternative.

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O-2

Wolbachia—Intracellular Microbes That Manipulate Reproductive Systems Of Arthropod Hosts

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More than 80% of the animal species in our planet are insects, which play important roles in an ecosystem as well as in human activities. A group of symbiotic bacteria, called Wolbachia, is of special interest because of their ability to manipulate the reproductive system of their hosts in various tactic ways. What Wolbachia do to their hosts include male-killing, feminization, the extinguishment of sex, and, as far as the formation of new species. Although detailed molecular mechanism of action for these effects is still unclear (possible involvement in mitotic and/or meiotic cell division and epigenetic DNA modification is suggested), all these effects lead to their spread in host populations. Wolbachia infection is widespread globally, detected from more than 40% of insect species, being one of the most successful bacteria on the planet. Wolbachia is currently applied on mosquitoes to combat the dengue fever disease in several countries. Here, I will talk about a latest discovery made in Wolbachia-infected butterflies and its implications in general biology. A potential use of Wolbachia in pest insect management will also be discussed.

Virus Like Particles A New Tool In Nanobiotechnology

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Viruses like Particles (VLPs) are empty cages carrying no genetic material but are similar to native virus. VLPs can be made using capsid proteins of the virus which have the ability to self fold and form VLPs of 50-200 nm size. VLPs can be characterized broadly into two classes based upon the presence or absence of lipid layer around VLPs. Our interest is with VLPs with lipid bilayer as it can provide a surface which can be utilized for producing multi-functional VLPs. We have displayed several proteins on VLPs like, Hemagglutinin from Influenza virus, recombinant short chain fragments targeting colon cancer tumor antigen-72 marker protein, human prorenin receptors respectively. VLPs can be easily prepared in silkworms using bacmid expression system and scaled up based upon requirement. Multi-functional macromolecular structures like VLPs can have application as future platforms for drug delivery system and vaccination system.

Here at shizuoka university we have good education and research environment for the development of students. India and Japan both needs young minds with firm grasp of science to push the respective countries future in next century. We have initiated Asia Bridge Program (ABP) and we accept each year 40 students in undergraduate program and 40 students in postgraduate program with scholarships.

Keywords: Nanobiotechnology, virus like particles, drug delivery system, vaccination, Asia Bridge Program

Ciguatera Fish Poisoning In Japan

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Ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP), one of the most frequent finfish poisoning in the world, affects 20,000-60,000 people annually. It is caused by consumption of marine finfish inhabiting coral reef area, contaminated with ladder shape polyether compounds, ciguatoxins (CTXs). CTXs are primarily produced by benthic dinoflagellate genus of *Gambierdiscus* and transferred to herbivorous animals and carnivorous fishes *via* food chain. Although, CFP mainly occurred in tropical and sub-tropical regions of the Pacific and the Indian Oceans, and Caribbean Sea, it has been reported from temperate area.

We analyzed the data of food poisonings reported by local governments to the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare (MHLW), Japan. In 1965-2010, there were 114 incidents which were mostly reported from Okinawa prefecture located in the subtropical region. There was no fatal case. Representative implicated fish species were snappers *Lutjanus bohar* and *L. monostigma*, Yellow-edged lyretail *Variola louti*, and Spotted Knifejaw *Oplegnathus punctatus* caught off the Okinawan Waters. Many of incidents occurred in Mainland Japan where locate temperate region, were due to consumption of the fish caught from tropical or subtropical sea with the exception of the incidents those *O. punctatus* implicated.

In most incidents, implicated fish were caught by patients or their relatives for self-consumption. Symptoms frequently reported were diarrhea, fatigue, tingling and pain on contact with cold. Even though there must have been many underreported cases, the investigation data of food poisonings previously obtained are useful to identify risk factors and to consider risk management strategies. A research project for strengthening CFP epidemiological investigation is necessary to improve data quality for future risk assessments.

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O-5

Ribosome-Mediated Site-Specific Incorporation Of Dipeptides And Dipeptidomimetics Into Proteins

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The current set of non-standard amino acid residues available for protein engineering is limited to α -amino acids. The ribosomal synthesis of peptides and proteins bearing non- α -amino acids such as β -amino acids and peptidomimetics has been challenging so far. Recently, we demonstrated that suitable mutations in the peptidyltransferase center (PTC) in the 23S rRNA of the ribosome can enable the incorporation of β -amino acids into proteins in an *in vitro* translation system.^{1,2} Here, we demonstrate that similar modifications in the PTC of ribosome can also facilitate *in vitro* biosynthesis of proteins containing peptidomimetics. Using a dipeptidyl-puromycin, different sets of ribosomes were selected from a random pool of ribosomes having mutations in two separate regions of the 23S rRNA. S-30 translation systems harboring mutant ribosomes were prepared for their use in *in vitro* protein synthesis.

Chemical aminoacylation methodology was used to prepare misacylated tRNA_{CUA}S and amber stop codon (TAG) suppression technology was utilized to synthesize proteins *in vitro*. Several mutant ribosomes site-specifically incorporated three dipeptides (GlyPhe, PheGly and PhePhe) and two dipeptidomimetics (PhethioGly and oxazole dipeptidomimetic) into full-length proteins including *E. coli* dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) and green fluorescent protein (GFP) with up to 15% efficiencies as compared to wild-type protein synthesis. Ribosome-mediated site-specific incorporation of a thioamide moiety (PhethioGly) into the backbone of a protein (DHFR) was also demonstrated for the first time. Two proteins, having a GFP-chromophore like synthetic fluorescent oxazole derivative, were prepared using mutant ribosomes, which had up to 20-times enhanced fluorescence intensity and slightly higher quantum yield as compared to GFP.

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O-6

Heat Waves And Cold Waves Over India

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India experiences heat waves during March to June and cold waves during November to February. In our recent study, using the India Meteorological Department high resolution temperature datasets, we tried to understand the causes of the heat/cold waves over India and the processes maintaining them. Our analysis shows that the heatwaves and cold waves over India are related to the sea surface temperature conditions in the Pacific and are mostly due to the quasi-stationary waves from the Pacific to India. Details of the processes responsible for the heat/cold waves will be presented in the talk.

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O-7

Cellulose Nanofiber Backboned Prussian Blue Nanoparticles As A Novel Adsorbent For The Elimination Of Radioactive Cesium

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On 11 March 2011, a magnitude-9 earthquake struck Tohoku, Japan and followed by the devastating Tsunami, a damageable amount of radionuclides had dispersed from the Fukushima Daiichi's damaged nuclear reactors. Decontamination of the spread radionuclides from seawater and soil, due to the huge amounts of coexisting competitive ions, has been the topmost difficulty. Prussian blue (PB), has been the most powerful material for selectively trapping the radioactive cesium ions. The high tendency of PB to form stable colloids in water, however, has restricted its applications in open-field radioactive cesium decontamination. A nano/nano combinatorial approach has provided an ultimate solution to this intrinsic colloid formation difficulty of PB. Cellulose nanofibers (CNF) were used to immobilize PB via the formation of CNF-backboned PB (CNF/PB). The CNF/PB was found to be highly stable in water and moreover, it gave a 139 mg/g capability and a million (10^6) order of magnitude distribution coefficient (K_d) for absorbing of the radioactive cesium ion. Field studies on soil and seawater decontaminations in Fukushima gave satisfactory results, proving high capabilities of CNF/PB for practical applications.

Molecular illustration of the CNF/ PB nanoparticles and a digital photo (inset) of CNF/PB powder

POSTERS P1-P8

Energy and Environmental

P1

Mathematical Modelling For Met-Ocean Design Studies At Single Point Mooring Off Hazira, Gulf Of Khambhath

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Gulf of Khambhath, lies between the coasts of Surat and Bharuch districts to the East and Ahmedabad and Bhavnagar districts to the west in the northern part of the Arabian Sea. Hazira is an established industrial township, about 25 km from the textile township of Surat, in the state of Gujarat, on the western coast of India. One of the fundamental aims of the author has been to determine the Met-Ocean dynamics as a function of time, for the Single Point Mooring (SPM) located off Hazira.

Though several studies were made earlier, Gulf of Khambhath is still not completely resolved and some more studies in different angles and with different methods are essential to understand the Met-Ocean condition for Gulf of Khambhath in a holistic manner. So presently, author's main objective of this study is to ascertain tidal currents, weather and wave pattern as well as return period in order to arrive at closest to actual Met Ocean data at Hazira SPM location. For the above context, the coupled numerical model was setup on the basis of the MIKE suite of models. Hydrodynamics and wave dynamics features are resolved in the simulations for giving into the input as an extreme value analysis process. And also, the design water level is considered as the combination of tidal and non-tidal components. Non-tidal components contributing to water level constitute of wave crest, storm surge, sea level rise by climate change and other meteorological disturbances.

The field campaign, available literature and the subsequent model studies have generated an understanding of the hydraulic conditions and determine the design value for the requirement. Hence, the model results reveal that the design water levels relative to the Chart Datum at the SPM for various return period years in 1, 5,10,20,50 & 100 are 12.3m, 13.2m, 13.5m, 17.9m, 20.4m & 23.5m respectively. The corresponding return period of design surface currents are 2.9m/s, 3.1m/s, 3.2 m/s, 3.3m/s, 3.5m/s & 3.8 m/s respectively.

P2

The Development Of A Hydrodynamic Model To Investigate The Effects Of Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) Drag Force On The Current Field.

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Coastal ecosystems with submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) facilitate sinking of particulate organic matter (POM). Therefore, the coastal ecosystem can play sustainable roles in climate change mitigation by the appropriate transplantation and conservation of SAV. The quantification of POM sinking and burial rate in vegetated areas considering the drag effect is critical in terms of estimation of the role of coastal ecosystems in climate change mitigation. Here we developed a new 3-D physical model and performed field observations to investigate the drag effect of SAV on current fields. The study site is the Furen Lagoon which is a semi-enclosed brackish lagoon (the area is 57.4km² and about 68% is covered with seagrass meadows). We carried out the model with two scenario cases i.e., “with-SAV” and “without-SAV” and compared with the observational data.

We found that the drag force of SAV interrupted the inflow of saline water from sea and fresh water from rivers and reduced the mixing. In addition, the with-SAV case showed a vertically unidirectional flow which is one of the hydrodynamic characteristics in the Furen lagoon. However the without-SAV case demonstrated that the current direction is an opposite between the surface and the bottom layers, thus the model indicated that SAV influences the vertical circulation of coastal shallow estuary.

In the future, the hydrodynamic model can be a tool to estimate the role of SAV in the mitigation of climate change by coupling with ecosystem models.

P3

Assessing Impact Of Economic Activities On Urban Air-Quality In India By Nightlight And Air Quality Remote Sensing Datasets

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Understanding causal relationship between economic activities and emissions is important for framing successful environmental policies. To study these relationships, continuous temporal and spatial urban ‘air quality’ data is required. In the absence of such data from ground measurements, we use remote sensing datasets to identify which economic activities can be a cause of urban air pollution. By classification of time-series data as per nightlight intensity (which has been found to correlate well with economic activities) and air quality intensities, inferences are drawn about transition in regional air quality and possible anthropogenic sources. Using these inferences, relationship between annual GDP of various economic sectors (such as construction, manufacturing, etc.) and air quality species at state-level is checked for correlation as well as causality using Granger’s test. The air quality species considered are angstrom exponent and aerosol optical depth (from MODIS satellite) and NO₂ and SO₂ (from OMI satellite). Nightlight time series data is obtained by intra-calibrating DN values from multiple-year DMSP-OLS sensors and inter-calibrating it with radiance values from VIIRS-DNB sensor. The objective is to identify which economic sectors correlate well with air quality species and can also be statistically identified as ‘Granger cause’. In general, we find secondary economic sectors (e.g. Industries, construction) as a Granger cause of air quality in Indian states with low GDP while for states with higher GDP, tertiary economic sectors (e.g. banking, trade and restaurants) have been identified as Granger cause. Also for 40% states we found Banking/Insurance, Construction and Industry sectors Granger caused AOD, ANG, SO₂ as well as NO₂.

P4

A Conceptual Framework Towards Forest Fire Mitigation Practice in Part of Indian Himalaya: A Coupled Human and Natural System

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India has a long history of regular forest burning which has led to shaping of the current unique landscape in the country. Himalayan ecosystem which is house to wide range of endemic species of flora and fauna, are threatened under the accelerated human influences. The considered ecosystem is peculiar in the way humans are embedded in this natural system. The close proximity of humans to the forest has made it accessible for various tangible and intangible deliverables. The dwellers of the forest fringe villages depend on forest for fuel wood, fodder for livestock, medicinal plant and many other non- timber forest products. Forest fires are a common feature in this region and the understanding about these fires and causative factors behind them still remains a constraint. The annual burning of forest as argued by many has been beneficial to only a relatively small avaricious fraternity of people resulting in short term gains, but it has undoubtedly created unequivocal and irrevocable loss to the natural system as a whole. Thus, there is a need for well-planned, scientifically correct mitigation policies to cut down the severity of forest fire.

Remote sensing and GIS are the robust tools available which can be used synergistically to link people vis-a-vis pixels, as they are affected on the ground. It provides a tool for manifestation of forest fire incidents, its socio- economic linkages with the landscape at spatio-temporal scales capturing the deeper analysis about various actors in the Coupled Human and Natural System of Indian Himalayas.

Keywords: Forest Fire, Mitigation, Remote Sensing, Coupled Human and Natural System

P5

Observation And Analysis Of Seafloor Resources Using Underwater Platforms

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Oceans are abundant in mineral resources, energy reserves and marine life whose exploration has gained significant interest in recent years due to its economic and scientific importance. Observation of such environments require custom built sensors, underwater platforms such as Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) or Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUV) that carry these sensors and means of deployment at target sites.

Our lab at the University of Tokyo has been developing sensing technologies and underwater platforms for various applications ranging from shallow rivers to deep oceans. A key focus area at present is the exploration of deep sea manganese crusts and nodules; for which we have developed a high resolution 3D colour mapping system, an acoustic sub-bottom thickness measurement probe and an AUV, called BOSS-A, to support these systems. Combining the observations from these sensors, we aim to estimate and analyse the distribution of such minerals in deep sea.

Fig. AUV BOSS-A with visual reconstruction and acoustic mapping sensors surveying manganese crust deposits

Other systems developed include a long range color 3D seafloor mapping technology to generate wide area detailed maps, which has been successfully deployed in sites such as hydrothermal vents, methane hydrate seeps and coral reefs. Combining the data from the mapping systems with data from other sources such as multibeam, physical and chemical sensors and analysing them with tools such as machine learning provides key insights into spatial and temporal variations, and physical and biological processes involved at scales from several square centimeters to global scales, which form key inputs in tackling global challenges.

P6

Detection Of Ciguatoxins From Finfish Caught Off The Tropical Sea.

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Ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP), associated with gastrointestinal, cardiovascular and neurological symptoms and signs is one of the largest scale food poisonings of non-microbial origins annually affecting 20,000–60,000 people worldwide. It occurred mainly in tropical and subtropical Indo-Pacific and Caribbean Sea due to consumption of finfish contaminated with principal toxins, ciguatoxins (CTXs).

In this study, we analyzed CTXs in tropical fish specimens purchased from local market in Trinidad and Tobago, Taiwan, Thailand, Philippines and Fiji where belonging tropical and sub-tropical regions. Totally 46 specimens were collected including snappers, groupers, barracuda, Spanish mackerel, and moray eel. Standards of CTXs for LC-MS/MS were prepared from natural resources such as toxic fish specimens and dinoflagellate *Gambierdiscus toxicus*, one of the producers of CTXs.

LC-MS/MS analysis revealed no CTXs was contaminated with specimens of Trinidad and Tobago, Taiwan, Thailand nor Philippines, CTX1B and CTX3C congeners were detected from two *V. louti* and moray eel, respectively, from those obtained from Fiji where recognized as CFP endemic area. CTXs profiles of the *V. louti* were similar to those of the specimens from Okinawa, Japan. Interestingly, no CTXs were detected from two specimens of *V. louti* purchased from Philippines neither *L. bohar* nor *L. monostigma* from Fiji. These three species are representative species causing CFP in Japan.

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P7

Comparison Of Digestive Capability Between Toxic And Non-Toxic Puffer Fish (*Takifugu Rubripes*): An Attempt To Determine The Role Of Puffer Toxin On The Digestion Process

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In our earlier study, we found the role of tetrodotoxin (TTX) on the metabolic efficiency of the enterobacteria (*Vibrio alginolyticus*) in the digestive tract of puffer with significant increase in the concentration of turbid byproduct in the case of the toxic samples compared to that of non-toxic ones, under both aerobic and anaerobic condition. Under the present study, we compared the digestion capability between the toxic and non-toxic puffers to have further insight into the role of TTX in the digestion process. We hatched the larvae of kusafugu, *Takifugu niphobles* from the fertilized eggs under standard laboratory condition, and the non-toxic cultured puffers were reared for approximately six months before dividing them into two groups. One group was fed with toxic feed and the other with non-toxic feed for ten days to prepare the toxic and non-toxic specimens. After five days of stopping the feed, five specimens from each group were fed with one shrimp per specimen. The puffers were dissected 180 minutes after ingestion of the shrimp, liver and intestine were taken out. The toxicity in the liver was measured using mouse assay, and the state of the digested contents was observed from the intestine, in both toxic and non-toxic groups for comparison. The toxicity in the liver sample from the non-toxic group of specimens was negligible (<20 MU/g.), while that of the toxic group of specimens had significantly higher toxicity. The state of digested contents in the toxic and non-toxic group of specimens was also distinctly different from each other. In 5 non-toxic specimens, the shape of the shrimp still remained intact, characterized by the undigested muscle and thicker shell. On the other hand, in 5 toxic specimens, the shape of the shrimp was hardly recognized, characterized by the digested muscle, and the shell remaining distinctly thin. The above results suggest that digestibility distinctly differs between non-toxic and toxic puffers. The turbid byproduct substance produced by intestinal bacteria as reported from our earlier study plausibly plays a significant role in the digestion capability of the toxic puffer.

P8

Adoption, Impact And Sustainable Management Of Medicinal Plant Cultivation For Alternative Income Generation In Tribal Communities In Gujarat

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Background Vasavas are a tribe from Gujarat state in India who have rich tradition of indigenous medicine and have traditionally practiced sustainable traditional subsistence farming. However, they are now economically and educationally deprived due to limited cash income sources. A possible sustainable way for their economic development is by creating alternative income sources in agriculture by using their understanding of medicinal plants. From an ethnobotanical study undertaken with this tribe, an informal self-help group, was established that promoted the cultivation of medicinal plants (MP) for generating additional cash income for them.

Research Objective: 1. Elucidating factors influencing adoption of this technology 2. Characterize growing environment of MP. In the first phase, we tried to find the intra-member differences that affect the intensity of adoption of MP cultivation technology as a source of generating additional income.

Methodology: Semi-structured questionnaire survey was conducted for all the members of the group and plants' ecophysiological data was collected in their agricultural field and/or home garden during February-March 2015, at Dediapada.

Results and discussion: One of the hypothesis is that access to stable income in the family would affect the level of adoption of this technology. Previous knowledge of medicinal plant doesn't seem to affect their decision to cultivate more plants. However the annual profit from selling of cultivated of MP was higher for farmers with stable income. Characterizing such factors can lead us to find to better solutions for intensifying level of adoption of cultivation of medicinal plants for generating higher income.

POSTERS P9-P24A

Engineering and Material Sciences

**(including JSPS-DST Asia Seminar 2016
posters)**

P9

Study Of Mechanical Mixing Mechanism For Sustainable Polymer Composite Based On Polypropylene/Flyash

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This project aims to develop a sustainable polymer composite by using Flyash (FA) as a filler to enhance the mechanical property of the Polypropylene (PP). Cost effectiveness and eco-friendliness are the two basic value proposition from this work. This composite can be used for various application areas like automobile components, household plastic utensils, warehouse plastic instruments etc. FA is an industrial waste which is a big problem to the society as its non-biodegradable therefore discharging is not easy & healthy. Recently lot of research have evolved focusing on the recyclability and reusability of FA and now it's often used in construction industry and have been classified as a geopolymer. It's an amorphous geopolymer which is mixed with PP using a twin screw extruder connected to a pelletiser with a loading of 10-40 %. The obtained pellets were given a shape using injection moulding for further testing. Tensile and flexural testing of the composite reveals that 30% loading of FA in PP helps in enhancing its mechanical property. The mechanism for such behaviour is explained in this work.

Local electron correlation effects on the quasiperiodic lattice

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Recent years, much attention has been paid to strongly correlation effects since the development of the system with various degrees of freedom such as the quasicrystalline system. An important feature is that the system does not have translational symmetry but rotational symmetry (e.g. 10-fold and 8-fold) which should yield nontrivial electric properties in the metallic quasicrystals [2]. Recently, quantum critical behavior in $\text{Au}_{51}\text{Al}_{34}\text{Yb}_{15}$ has experimentally been realized [3], which stimulates further theoretical and experimental investigations on electron correlations in these systems. To clarify how electron correlations affect low temperature properties in these systems, we employ the Hubbard model on the Penrose lattice [4]. Using the real-space dynamical mean-field theory, we clarify that electron properties strongly depends on the lattice site and its geometry when the system is metallic in the quasiperiodic system. Moreover, we find a temperature dependent distribution of local quantities characteristic of the Penrose lattice. This behavior originates from the local isomorphism which holds high geometrical regularity even if there are no translational symmetry, which leads to an emergence of nontrivial superconductivity formed by unconventional spatially extended Cooper pairs in the case of the attractive Hubbard model [5].

Figure: Offsite pair amplitude $OP_{ij} \equiv \langle c_i^\uparrow c_j^\downarrow \rangle$ (normalized by local pair amplitude) plotted against the Euclidean distance $\|r_i - r_j\|$ for extended pairs (circles), short-ranged pairs (triangles) and localized pairs (crosses). Inset: Enlarged view for the short-distance part.

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P11

Effect Of Phase Stability On Deformation Behavior Under Tensile And Cyclic Loading In Fe-Mn-Si Shape Memory Alloy

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Fe-Mn-Si alloys are well known to exhibit a shape memory effect associated with a deformation-induced martensitic transformation from γ -austenite (face centered cubic structure) to ϵ -martensite (hexagonal close-packed structure) and its reversion on subsequent heating. Recently, it was reported that the Fe-Mn-Si alloys exhibit superior low-cycle fatigue properties due to a reversible $\gamma \leftrightarrow \epsilon$ transformation under cyclic push-pull loading. Fe-Mn-Si alloys show various deformation modes depending on the phase stabilities and the stacking fault energy of γ -austenite. In this report, the effect of phase stability on deformation behavior under tensile and cyclic loading in Fe-28Mn-6Si-6Cr (mass %) shape memory alloy was investigated at various deformation temperatures. Tensile fracture test and low-cycle fatigue test at a total strain range of 0.02 were applied to the alloys at deformation temperatures ranging from -50 to 250°C. Characteristic temperatures of M_s^σ and M_d were determined as 100°C and 200°C, respectively. The total elongation increased with deformation temperature accompanied by continuous strain-hardening with delayed formation of ϵ -martensite. The highest fatigue life of 22,400 cycles was obtained at 150°C just below M_d . The deformation modes are determined as deformation-induced martensitic transformation, ϵ -slip, and γ -slip below M_d , and γ -slip and γ -twinning above M_d . The highest fatigue life was obtained at the deformation temperature between M_s^σ and M_d , and at the stacking fault energy of around 15 mJ/m².

P12

Synthesis and magnetic properties of Au-Al-Gd approximants

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Tsai-type Quasicrystal approximants are periodic crystals that have the same local structure as the corresponding Tsai-Type quasicrystals. These compounds are made of the common Tsai-type icosahedral cluster. The Tsai-type cluster contains a rare-earth icosahedron shell. Recently, the existence of a long-range magnetic order was reported in Cd₆Tb and Au-SM-R (SM=Si,Ge,Sn) approximants [1-3]. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate the magnetic properties of other Tsai-type compounds that are also composed of the same Tsai-type clusters. In the present work, we have studied the phase constitution and magnetic properties in the Au-Al-Gd systems [4].

Polycrystalline alloys of nominal compositions of Au-Al-Gd were prepared by arc-melting high-purity (>99.9wt%) Au, Al, Gd. The alloys were annealed under an Ar atmosphere. The phase purity of the samples was examined by powder X-ray diffraction using CuK α radiation. The temperature and field dependence of the magnetization were measured using a SQUID or VSM magnetometer. The specific heat was measured using MPMS.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies have shown that a single phase is obtained in an extraordinarily wide Au/Al range with 14 at% Gd. Also, the lattice parameter is found to increase with increasing the Au/Al ratio. Magnetic measurements have exhibited a salient composition-driven spin-glass to ferromagnetic transition in the approximant crystal for the first time. An interesting feature for Au-Al-Gd is that the paramagnetic Curie temperature, Θ_p , is clearly dependent on the Au/Al ratio. Θ_p increases significantly from a large negative value to a large positive value as the Au content increases. The behavior of Θ_p is explained based on the RKKY oscillation. Detailed results of the magnetic properties will be reported in the presentation.

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P13

Hot Working Flow Behavior And Processing Map Of Ti-6242S Alloy

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Hot working flow behavior of as-received Ti-6242S alloy was investigated by compression tests over the temperature range of 973 – 1373 K and strain rate range of $1 \times 10^{-3} - 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Processing map was developed at true strain (ϵ) = 0.5. The optimum processing conditions were found to be in the temperature range of 1173 – 1273 K, for strain rate ranges of $5 \times 10^{-1} - 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $10^{-3} - 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. Activation energy (Q) stress exponent (n) and threshold stress (σ_{th}) were also estimated to understand the deformation mechanism. An attempt was made to compare the flow localization parameter (α) and temperature sensitivity (S) with instability parameter of processing map (ξ) with in the processing map regime. Similarly, processing map for heat treated Ti-6242S alloy was also developed and compared in the selected temperature range of 1173 – 1323 K. The variation in stable and unstable regions of processing maps were explained with microstructural evolutions using optical microscope and scanning electron microscope.

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P14

Effects Of Interface Material On Decay Of Dynamic Response Of Free And Controlled Rocking Systems

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Use of unbonded post-tensioned rocking walls as earthquake energy dissipation devices is gaining popularity because of the capability of re-centering the structure after an earthquake and the ease of installation for retrofitting purposes. Rocking is the primary active mechanism in such structural members, whereas impact at wall base is the primary cause of energy dissipation. In order to understand the intricacies associated with the rocking mechanism, simple free and controlled rocking blocks are investigated to study the effect of introduction of different interface materials. Introduction of an interface material alters the general behavior of a rocking system, as the energy dissipation mechanism and the contact conditions change. The present study focuses on developing finite element model of rocking systems with and without interface material, with the objective of capturing and quantifying the associated energy dissipation mechanisms. Results from this investigation can be used to develop efficient ways to prevent crushing of corner concrete which is the major cause of damage in such systems.

P15

Effect Of High Pressure Torsion On Mechanical And Tribological Behavior Of Calcium Hexaboride Reinforced AZ31 Magnesium Composites

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Effect of High pressure torsion (HPT) on AZ31 Magnesium composites reinforced by calcium hexaboride (0, 2, 3 and 4 wt. %) on mechanical and tribological behavior has been studied. HPT was conducted at room temperature under 5 GPa pressure at 1 rpm rotation speed with several number of rotations (N=0, ¼, and 5). The microstructural observation in TEM shows that a large refinement in grain size was achieved at N = 5. The initial grain size of the as-cast AZ31 Mg composites (~ 130 µm) were reduced to nano meter level (~ 80 nm). Due to the grain refinement the micro-hardness of the AZ31 Mg composites were increased from 64.4 ± 6.4 Hv (as-cast) to 137.9 ± 6.6 Hv (HPT, N=5). Similarly, the dry sliding wear test was conducted in the linear ball on disk tribometer at room temperature against SUJ-2 grade bearing steel ball with 4 N load, 40 mm/s sliding velocity for 100 m sliding distance. The grain refined AZ31 Mg composites offers reduced wear rate of 9 x 10⁻³ µg/m compared to 12 x 10⁻³ µg/m of as-cast AZ31 Mg composites. It is observed from analysis of SEM images of wear debris that the severe wear mechanism of the delamination wear was controlled in HPT AZ31 Mg composites. It is due to less possibility of crack nucleation in ultrafine grain structures.

Keywords: High pressure torsion, Magnesium composite, Hardness, Tribological behaviour

P16

Synthesis And Magnetic Properties Of The Au-Al-Yb Approximant

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Various phenomena such as a quantum critical state and superconductivity have been observed in Tsai-type intermediate valence quasicrystals and approximants [1] [2]. In these compounds, the Yb valence can be varied by applying the pressure [3] [4]. However, so far, there has been no report on the composition dependence of intermediate valence in these systems. Recently, it has been reported that the Au-Al-Gd approximant has a wide single phase region accompanying a systematic change of the magnetism [5]. In the present work, we have investigated the single phase region of the Au-Al-Yb approximant and studied the composition dependence of the Yb valence. Polycrystalline alloys of nominal compositions of $\text{Au}_x\text{Al}_{86-x}\text{Yb}_{14}$ ($x = 52-64$) were prepared by arc-melting high-purity (>99.9 wt%) Au, Al, Yb. The alloys were annealed under an Ar atmosphere. The phase purity of the samples was examined by powder X-ray diffraction using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation. The temperature and field dependence of the magnetization were measured using SQUID and VSM in the temperature range between 1.8 K and 300 K and fields of up to 9 T. The Yb valence of the Au-Al-Yb approximant at room temperature were measured by Yb L_3 -edge x-ray absorption near-edge structure (XANES) spectroscopy in BL22XU at SPring-8. Powder X-ray diffraction studies have shown that a single phase is obtained in a wide Au/Al range with 14 at% Yb. The lattice parameter is found to increase drastically within a specific composition range. The temperature dependence of magnetic susceptibility is found to be strongly dependent on the composition, suggesting the change of the Yb valence in the Au-Al-Yb approximant. Details of the magnetic measurements will be presented in the poster.

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P17

Flexibility and Conductivity Correlation between Polyaniline and Polystyrene-*block*-poly(2-vinylpyridine) (PS-*b*-P2VP) Based Nanocomposite

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Correlation between flexibility and conductivity was studied using polyaniline (PANI)/polystyrene-*b*-2-vinylpyridine (PS-*b*-P2VP) block copolymer nanocomposites. PANI/PS-*b*-P2VP nanocomposites was prepared by *in-situ* polymerisation of aniline and formation of nanostructure was simultaneously occurred during polymerization assisted by micellar formation of PS-*b*-P2VP in the polymerization solvent. The volume ratio of PS was varied while the molecular weight constant for the each nanocomposite sample. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analyses confirmed the presence of both PANI and PS-*b*-P2VP in each nanocomposite sample. Scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy revealed the nanostructure (spherical, connected spherical and cylindrical) can be manipulated by changing the volume fraction of PS. Wide angle X-ray diffraction data indicated less crystallized structure of PANI with the spherical nanostructure. Young's moduli for most flexible nanocomposite was 1 MPa although it was least conductive (i.e., $8.4 * 10^{-8}$ S cm⁻¹). It was found that spherical structure of PANI drastically improved the mechanical property but sacrificed the conductivity.

Unusual Reactivity Of Dithiol Protected Clusters In Comparison To Monothiol Protected Clusters: Studies Using Ag₅₁BDT₁₉ And Ag₂₉BDT₁₂

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We report the synthesis and unique reactivity of a new green dithiol protected cluster (DTPC), Ag₅₁BDT₁₉ (BDT, 1,3-benzenedithiol). The cluster composition was confirmed by electrospray ionization (ESI) and matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) mass spectrometric studies as well as by other supporting data. Surprisingly, the chemical reactivity between this DTPC and Au₂₅(SR)₁₈ involves only metal ion exchange in Au₂₅(SR)₁₈ without any ligand exchange, while reactions between monothiol protected clusters (MTPCs) show both metal and ligand exchange, an example being the reaction between Ag₂₅DMBT₁₈ and Au₂₅PET₁₈ (where DMBT and PET are 2,4-dimethylbenzenethiol and phenylethanethiol, respectively). The conclusions have been confirmed by the reaction of another DTPC, Ag₂₉BDT₁₂ with Au₂₅BT₁₈ (where BT corresponds to butanethiol) in which only metal exchange happens in Au₂₅BT₁₈. We also show the conversion of Ag₅₁BDT₁₉ to Ag₂₉BDT₁₂ in presence of a second monothiol, DMBT which does not get integrated to the product cluster. This is completely different from the previous understanding wherein reaction between MTPCs with a second thiol leads to either mixed thiol protected cluster with the same core composition or a completely new cluster core protected with the second thiol. The present study exposes a new avenue of research for monolayer protected clusters, which in turn will give additional impetus to explore the chemistry of DTPCs.

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Stable Gas Phase Unprotected Clusters Of Noble Metals In Air From Protected Clusters In Solution

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Gas phase clusters¹ of noble metals, prepared by electrospray ionization of solution, have been investigated extensively in vacuum². However such clusters have not been known to exist in ambient conditions till date. In a recent series of experiments we have found that systematic desorption of ligands can be achieved starting from monolayer protected clusters leading to unprotected clusters in the gas phase. In our experiments cationic metal naked clusters were generated by passing the ligand protected clusters through a heated tube outside the mass spectrometer. Such clusters were prepared in ambient conditions enabling their reactions in air. We present some of the results wherein, hydride and phosphine protected cluster³ Ag₁₈H₁₅(PPH₃)₁₀ results in Ag¹⁸⁺ and Ag¹⁷⁺ bare clusters without mass selection. Unlikely the thiolate protected clusters produce fragments of metal thiolate under identical process and no naked clusters were observed.

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Stability Of Monolayer Protected Clusters Towards Dissociation

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Ligand protected noble metal clusters, consisting of a precise number of atoms, possess extraordinary stability which is primarily due to geometric as well as electronic factors.¹ They are becoming increasingly important in many aspects of sustainability. Understanding the dissociation pathways of these clusters help in their structure elucidation. The most widely studied nanocluster, Au₂₅(SR)₁₈ is known to dissociate through the loss of Au₄(SR)₄ fragment.² However, understanding the thermodynamics and kinetics of these fragmentation processes is quite challenging. Herein, we report an attempt to probe into the energy demand of cluster fragmentation using collision induced dissociation. Energy resolved collisions with a series of ions of clusters Ag₂₉(S₂R)₁₂, Ag₂₅(SR)₁₈ and Ag₄₄(SR)₃₀ reveal distinct fragmentation kinetics involving charge separation. Such studies are important in understanding the stability as well as the stages of growth and nucleation of clusters.

Figure 1. A) Schematic of the fragmentation pathways and B) collision energy resolved fragmentation curves of $[Ag_{29}(BDT)_{12}]^{3-}$ ion. Collision energy is in laboratory scale. Inset a) shows the survival yield curve plotted as a function of centre-of-mass energy (E_{COM}).

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Highly Luminescent Monolayer Protected Ag₅₆Se₁₃S₁₅ Clusters

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Semiconductor quantum dots with high fluorescence quantum yields and negligible photobleaching have attracted intense research interest owing to their wide range of applications in bioimaging, sensing, light harvesting etc. [1-2]. Quantum clusters are a new class of materials consisting of a finite number of atoms, usually a few tens or hundreds, with unique physical and chemical properties [3]. Quantum clusters of gold and silver are well known. Ag₂S and Ag₂Se quantum dots have been studied to some extent, but their clusters are unknown. Herein, a highly luminescent (quantum yield 21%) mixed chalcogenide silver cluster, Ag₅₆Se₁₃S₁₅ cluster of Ag₂X stoichiometry, protected with 4-tert-butyl benzyl mercaptan ligand has been synthesized and characterized. Collective investigation from diverse tools of analyses such as mass spectrometry, elemental analysis, thermogravimetry and X-ray diffraction point to this composition. The cluster emits in the solution and in the solid state and has been deposited on oxide supports to get red emitting films. The specificity of cluster emission to mercuric ion, among a range of heavy metal ions has been used to develop a sensor, which shows sensitivity down to 1 ppb. A pH paper-like visual detector has been developed by combining the Hg(II)-sensitive emission of the cluster and insensitive emission of fluorescein isothiocyanate. The test strip shows visual detection down to 1 ppb in real water samples.

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Solution Based Fabrication Of A Fast Response, Broad-Band, Large Area Photodetector

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High speed, sensitive photodetectors are essential in imaging and optical communication applications. However, the laborious fabrication processes and the costs involved set hurdles for technology realization of such devices. Herein, we report a simple cost effective solution based method of fabricating high performance photodetectors based on Au nanopyramidal structures grown on Silicon substrate by an electroless process. These nanostructures reduce the reflectivity of Si in the infrared region thus enhancing light trapping and absorption. The device exhibits a high on/off ratio of 10^3 at room temperature. Its excellent responsivity, ~ 310 mA/W in wide range of wavelengths, and fast response, ~ 40 μ s, are promising in the context of various optoelectronic applications. The device can be realized on mm² areas while maintaining uniformity of the response. This method enabled us to realize a 5x5 image sensor which displayed appreciable performance.

**Thermodiffusion Driven Formation Of SERS Substrates For Gas-Phase
And Liquid-State Analytical Detection**

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Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) has been a powerful technique for ultra-sensitive detection of analyte from liquid-phase. Two important practical limitations of SERS have been its inability to (a) detect molecules directly from gas-phase and (b) provide reproducible and quantifiable SERS intensities. Here, we address these two long-standing challenges by developing a SERS substrate consisting of nanoparticle assemblies formed by thermal-diffusion, under the influence of thermal gradient. Such nanoparticle assemblies formed by thermal diffusion are called Soret colloids, drawing parallel to the Soret effect that pertains to ion-diffusion under thermal gradient and is critical to understand phenomena such as ion-transport across biological membranes and variations in salt concentrations of oceans.

Under thermal gradient induced by controlled cooling of the colloidal nanoparticles system, a fraction of the nanoparticles migrates towards the colder region and assemble as aggregates while the isolated nanoparticles are located at the hot end. Such a process is universally observed across a range of nanomaterials, irrespective of their size, shape, chemical constitution or surface functionality. It is observed that the kinetics of formation of Soret colloids depends upon the extent of cooling and the size of nanoparticles. Such Soret colloids contain a highly mono-disperse SERS “hot spots” density, critical to achieve reproducible and quantifiable SERS intensities. These Soret colloids function as an excellent Surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) substrate for reliable, quantitative detection of industrial dye (Rhodamine 6G) and chemical explosives (2,4,6 Trinitro toluene) from both liquid-phase and gas-phase. The liquid-state sensitivity down to less than 10 molecules of chemical explosive (TNT), and gas-phase sensitivity of few parts-per-million of TNT has been demonstrated. Thus, this work enables an important step towards employing SERS for direct and facile gas phase analytical detection.

H-Bond Regulated Distinct Functional Group Display In Vesicular Assembly Of Unsymmetrical Bola-Shape π -Amphiphiles

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Considering enormous importance of vesicles in biological applications we envisioned it would be of significant interest to decorate inner and outer membrane of a vesicle with distinctly different functional groups, which still remains a challenge in this well-studied system. With this aim we have studied structurally similar unsymmetrical bola-amphiphiles (Scheme 1) which consist of a NDI-chromophore attached hydrazide group as the hydrophobic domain and two different water soluble segments (anionic and non-ionic) attached in specific manner to core. First of all, NDI-3 that lacks a hydrophobic shielding due to the lack of the benzene ring, does not show facile self-assembly in water. On the other hand rest of the candidates exhibit spontaneous and stable monolayer vesicle structures in water which has been established by electron microscopy, SANS, dynamic light scattering and spectroscopy studies. Interestingly they exhibit thermoresponsive vesicle to micelle transition due to the LCST behaviour exhibited by self-assembled hydrophilic wedge.

Scheme 1: Chemical structures of unsymmetrical bolaamphiphiles

In all these cases, self-assembly was dictated by H-bonding among the hydrazide group which resulted in unidirectional orientation leading to the formation of unsymmetrical membrane. Furthermore, owing to the preference of the H-bonded chain to remain located at the inner wall, functional group display in these vesicles could be fully dictated by the location of the hydrazide group. For example between NDI-1 and NDI-2, depending on the location of the hydrazide group, the former formed an anionic vesicle while the latter showed vesicular structures with non-ionic outer surface. On the other hand, amongst NDI-1, NDI-4 and NDI-5, all of which formed anionic vesicle, the size and surface charge density could be precisely tuned depending on the nature of the anionic head group. These distinct self-assembly modes resulted in very different ability of these vesicles for electrostatic interaction driven biomolecular recognition which was thoroughly studied by testing their ability to bind with a cationic protein Chymotrypsin and inhibit its enzymatic activity. This presentation will focus on the structure-property relationship studies with these newly arrived π -amphiphiles.

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POSTERS P25-P39

Life Sciences and Biotechnology (and miscellaneous)

P25

Most Active And Responsive Site For Motilin- And Ghrelin-Induced Gastric Contractions Is Proximal Stomach In Asian Musk Shrew Stomach *In Vitro*

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Background and Aim: During the interdigestive state, motilin and ghrelin are released to regulate and initiate the phase III contractions of migrating motor complex (MMC). Previously, we observed that motilin and ghrelin synergistically induced gastric contraction *in vitro* and *in vivo*. These coordinated cyclic motor patterns originate from the stomach and propagate downward in the alimentary canal. On the basis of this, we hypothesized that certain regions in the stomach are more responsive to motilin and ghrelin, and strong gastric contractions are propagated from such responsive sites. Therefore, we aimed to find the active responsive site for motilin- and ghrelin-induced gastric contractions in the stomach.

Methods: We examined motilin- and/or ghrelin-induced gastric contractile patterns in different parts of the shrew stomach using an organ bath system. Treatment with tetrodotoxin and atropine was carried out to determine the involvement of the neural pathway. We performed q-PCR analysis to measure the mRNA expression of the motilin receptor, GPR38. We also examined the distribution of ghrelin-producing cells and GHSR mRNA expression in different parts of the shrew stomach using immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR, respectively.

Results: The *in vitro* study revealed, only the proximal corpus induced gastric contraction even at a motilin concentration of 10^{-10} M, while strong contractions were induced at a motilin concentration of 10^{-9} M in all the other parts of the stomach. Ghrelin (10^{-11} - 10^{-7} M) with pretreatment of a low dose of motilin (10^{-10} M) induced gastric contraction in a dose-dependent manner only in the fundus and proximal corpus but not in the distal corpus and antrum. These contractions were mediated by the cholinergic neural pathway in the myenteric plexus. GPR38 mRNA expression was higher in the proximal corpus than in the other segments. Ghrelin cell density and GHSR mRNA expression were also higher in the fundus and proximal corpus than in other parts.

Conclusions: These results suggest that the motilin and ghrelin reactivity is not consistent throughout the stomach. The fundus and proximal corpus are most sensitive and responsive to motilin- and ghrelin-induced synergistic gastric contractions suggesting that the proximal stomach is the most active site for the onset of MMC contraction.

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Synthesis Of Gb₃ Polymers As Neutralizer Against Shiga Toxin O:157 Strain

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Globotriaose (*Gala1-4Galβ1-4Glcβ1*) is one of the targets of **Shiga toxins** (Stxs), which are produced by Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) in humans, including **O157:H7** and also known as a trisaccharide moiety of globotriaosyl ceramide (**Gb₃**). A convenient synthesis of Gb₃ monomer derivative has been carried out by the means of various organic synthetic methods and chemical modifications to provide a water-soluble glycomonomer. In this research, galactose derivative was used as a donor and lactose derivative as an acceptor to synthesize a trisaccharide Gb₃ *via* glycosylation¹. After complete synthesis of acetylated Gb₃ monomer, anomeric deprotection was accomplished by *transamidation* reaction followed by *imidate* formation. Here, using a Gb₃ monomer with a C₆ length linker tethering the trisaccharide we are aiming to construct the glycopolymers having globotriaosyl moieties as pendant-type epitopes *via* homopolymerization and copolymerization with acrylamide. The shiga toxin B subunit (StxB), which is involved in cell membrane attachment and trafficking of Shiga holotoxin, binds specifically to the glycosphingolipid Gb₃, therefore we are aiming to check the binding affinity between synthetic Gb₃ polymers with StxB by the method of surface plasmon resonance (SPR) and the neutralizing effect of such polymers against the Stxs. Different structures of Gb₃ polymers can be synthesized and more to be synthesized in future so that the world can get rid of STEC attack.

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Honeybee Propolis Possess Anticancer Activity: Bioactives, Bioactivities And Bioavailability

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Honey is a well-known product of honeybees. It has a variety of health promoting activities. Another natural substance produced by honeybees is propolis or bee glue. It is sticky substance honeybees make by mixing their saliva with pine tree resin and other botanical sources. Known for a variety of bioactivities, New Zealand propolis has recently been quoted for its anticancer activity with Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester (CAPE) as a key anticancer component. In order to get molecular insights to the molecular mechanism of anticancer activity of CAPE, we performed cDNA array on the control and CAPE-treated breast cancer cells. We identified activation of DNA damage signaling, involving upregulation of GADD45 α and p53 tumor suppressor proteins. Bioinformatics and molecular docking analyses showed that CAPE is capable of disrupting mortalin-p53 complexes. We present experimental evidence to the disruption of mortalin-p53 complexes, nuclear translocation and activation of p53 by CAPE resulting in growth arrest in cancer cells. Furthermore, we demonstrate that whereas CAPE was unstable in the cell culture medium and hence showed low activity, its complex with gamma cyclodextrin (γ CD) showed high efficacy *in vitro* and *in vivo*. γ CD also increased the anticancer potential of supercritical extracts of Brazilian propolis with Artepillin-C as a major bioactive compound. The data proposes that γ CD is useful for enhancing the anticancer activity of honeybee propolis.

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NEW (Natural Efficient Economic & Welfare) Drugs For Preventive And Therapeutic Treatment Of Stress, Cancer And Neurodegenerative Diseases

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Stress, a highly complex factor, affects body functions in multitude of ways. It is recognized by nervous system as a disturbance in milieu intérieur. Capacity of body to cope up with such changes declines with age, and is related to age-related pathologies including neurodegeneration and cancer (highly stressed physiological states). Oxidative and DNA damage induced stress has been established to be a significant contributor to these phenomena and hence anti-stress compounds possess preventive and therapeutic potential. Our group earlier identified anticancer activity in the leaves of Ashwagandha and has defined mechanisms involved in selective killing of cancer cells. The active phytochemicals (Withanolides) caused oxidative stress to cancer cells. At the same time, they were shown to protect normal cells against a variety of stresses. We currently screened few natural compounds, using cell-based stress survival assays, to identify new NEW (Natural Efficient Economic & Welfare) drugs for preventive and therapeutic treatment of stress, cancer and neurodegenerative diseases. Oxidatively stressed human normal (TIG-3, fibroblasts) and cancer (U2OS, osteosarcoma) cells were subjected to recovery with or without the drugs. In these assays, we identified 'Cuc' as an anticancer and anti-stress compound, and demonstrated the molecular mechanism of its effect either alone or in combination with 'Wi-N', a known withanolide. Combination (CucWi-N) sensitized cancer cells to stress, implicating its value as adjuvant in cancer treatment. Interestingly, its low doses caused differentiation glial cancer (C6, rat brain glioma) cells, and protected them from oxidative stress suggesting its value for stress and age related diseases.

CARF Regulates Cell Proliferation In Two Directions: Stop And Go!

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CARF (Collaborator of ARF) was first cloned as an ARF (alternative reading frame)-interacting protein in our laboratory and has been shown to interact with multiple proteins including p53-tumor suppressor, HDM2 and beta-catenin proteins. It controls cell proliferation in two directions in a dose dependent way. Whereas high level of CARF expression resulted in growth arrest in cultured cancer cells, its super-high expression showed pro-proliferation and malignant transformation effects. CARF-compromised cells undergo apoptosis suggesting that it is an essential protein and may serve as a target for cancer therapy. We have reported that (i) CARF stabilizes ARF and p53 proteins, and down-regulates HDM2 (p53-antagonist) resulting in upregulation of p53-p21 axis (ii) it regulates DNA damage response of cancer cells in a dose-dependent way (iii) it acts as a transcriptional repressor of p21 resulting in enhanced cell proliferation and malignant transformation, especially in p53 compromised cells. Consistent with these CARF-mediated feed-forward and feedback controls on p53-p21 pathway, it was seen to increase during replicative and as well as stress induced cell senescence. Furthermore, cells that escape senescence were seen to possess super-high levels of CARF. These studies have shown that CARF controls cell proliferation by providing dose-dependent “Stop and Go” signals.

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Skin Pigmentation Is A Stress Response: Molecular Evidence To The Role Of Stress Protein, Mortalin

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Environmental factors, especially UV affects our skin coloration, a popular criteria of beauty. Understanding of biology of skin color is an important aspect of functional cosmetics, treatment of moles and dark spots. In order to identify cellular factors involved in skin color, we established cell based OAG (diacylglycerol 1 -oleoyl-2-acetyl-sn-glycerol) induced pigmentation assay and performed shRNA-mediated loss-of-function screening. By the four rounds of screenings, we identified 40 shRNAs that abolished OAG induced melanogenesis. Gene targets of the selected shRNAs were considered as candidate cellular factors crucial for pigmentation. These genes/proteins were identified to be involved in the regulation of cell proliferation, apoptosis, stress responses and mitochondrial functions by Bioinformatics and pathway analyses. In this study, we investigated the role of mortalin, mitochondrial stress chaperone, in melanogenesis. We demonstrate that mortalin is an important regulator of melanogenesis. Whereas its increase was associated with OAG and UV induced melanogenesis, its downregulation by shRNA or inhibitor compromised the process. Furthermore, we found that mortalin is upregulated in clinical samples of keloids. Taken together, we report mortalin is a useful marker for skin pigmentation and hence valuable for cosmetics and therapeutic manipulation of stress and other pathologies that affect skin color and other characteristics.

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5'-Aza-2'-Deoxycytidine Is A Multi-Target Anticancer Drug: Bioinformatics And Experimental Evidence

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Cancer is well established as a multifactorial disease and requires multi-module therapeutics. Increasing incidence of cancer has prioritized research on development of anticancer drugs. Search for new drugs and their approval by FDA takes a long time. Keeping this in view, research on new functions of FDA-approved anticancer drugs is desired to expand the list of multi-module functioning drugs for cancer therapy. In this study, we conducted an analysis for new functions of 5'-Aza-2'-deoxycytidine (5-Aza-dC), widely known anticancer drug, by applying the bio-chemo-informatic approach. It causes genome wide hypomethylation resulting into expression of several tumor suppressor genes resulting in growth arrest of cancer cells. The potential of 5-Aza-dC bioactivity was analyzed by PASS online and Molinspiration. Target proteins were predicted by SuperPred. The Protein Networks and Biological Processes were analyzed by Biological Networks using Gene Ontology tool, BINGO, based on BIOGRID database. Interactions between 5-Aza-dC with the targeted protein was examined by Autodoc Vina integrated into pyrx software. Induction of p53 by 5-Aza-dC was tested *in vitro* using cancer cells. Bioinformatics analyses predicted that 5-Aza-dC functions as a p53 inducer, radio-sensitizer, and inhibitor of some enzymes. It was predicted to target proteins including MDM2, POLA1, POLB, and CXCR4 that are involved in induction of DNA damage response and p53-p21 signaling. In order to investigate its new regulatory targets experimentally, we also performed loss-of-function miRNA screening and found induction of miRNA-335 that targeted CARF and several cell cycle regulatory proteins leading to growth suppression in cancer cells. Taken together, we demonstrate that 5-Aza-dC-induced senescence is a multi-module phenotype regulated not only by proteins but also by noncoding miRNAs.

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Studies On Sodium-Calcium Exchanger Gene (*NCX10*) In Rice In Response To Salt Stress

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Agricultural productivity is severely affected by abiotic stresses like salinity stress. It is estimated that 20 % of cultivated land and nearly half of the irrigated land is affected by salinity stress. Hence, genetic improvement of plants for tolerance to salinity will be helpful in achieving targeted food production to meet the demands of growing population. A common approach of salinity tolerance is the adequate control of salt uptake at the root level, regulation of influx into cells, control over long distance transport, and the compartmentation of ions.

Ion transporters provide important bases for salinity tolerance in plants. In our research, we have studied one of the rice ion transporter sodium calcium exchanger type 10 (*OsNCX10*) and their possible role in salt stress. The sodium calcium exchanger (NCX) is an antiporter membrane protein responsible for transport of Na⁺ and Ca²⁺. Our studies in yeast using yeast mutant 9.3 found that *OsNCX10* gene is responsible for salt susceptibility and it is also observed that *OsNCX10* helps to tolerate high potassium level in cell. Possibly, *OsNCX10* is potassium dependent sodium calcium exchanger. In quantitative real time PCR assay it is observed that expression of *OsNCX10* gene is upregulated during salt stress, gene expression was prominent in root as compared to leaf and shoot. We have also identified homologous *NCX10* gene in the other rice family species like *Puccinellia tenuiflora*, *Poa annuae* and *Pennisetum glaucum*. It shows that *OsNCX10* gene is highly conserved in poaceae family.

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Studies On *Arabidopsis thaliana* For Lateral Root Development And Root Skewing

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Roots act as anchor to provide support and nutrients to the plants body above the soil, to do so roots has to develop an complex architecture, like divergence in growth pattern, difference in length or variability in the spreading with lateral branching. When the primary roots get diverted from main path and forms an angle of inclination is called root skewing and secondary branches emerging from main primary branch are termed as lateral roots. However, the literature, regarding the movement of plant shoots is very large and regarding root is relatively scarce. Although we know that recently there is quite good progress in the plants, *Arabidopsis thaliana* is considered as a best experimental material for the study of root phenotypes due to ease of experiments and same have been used in the following study .

Here in this study considering above two phenotypes Genome wide association study was carried out with 245 natural accessions of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Around 12 genes were showing SNP's association. The q-RT PCR shows an even expression of these genes in root and shoot of *Arabidopsis thaliana* . In order to analyze the observed association on molecular level, mutants of the genes were grown on hard 1.5% agar (root skewing) and soft 0.8% agar (lateral root) medium. Out of 12, two genes (Ribosomal 5s protein gene and Unknown gene on chr no. 5) were able to show root-skewing phenotype significantly and one gene (3-ketoacyl carrier protein synthase KAS1) was showing significant increase in lateral root primordial. Homology study shows that Ribosomal 5s protein gene is conserved through whole eukaryote domain while unknown gene and KAS1 are exclusive to *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

However further analysis is needed to confirm the association of these genes with the respective phenotype.

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Formulation And Characterization Of Submicron O/W Emulsions Encapsulating Black Cumin Seed Oil

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Cancer has proved its global burden as evidenced by continually rising disease statistics. Synthetic compounds developed to attack against it are often associated with severe toxic effects, and are not easily affordable. Validation of affordable and efficient natural compounds against the disease is urgently mandated. Thymoquinone, one of the natural bioactives, derived from *Nigella sativa* sp., has been suggested for its beneficial effects against cancer, etc. However, reduced bioavailability and solubility in aqueous based solvents are the limitations associated with thymoquinone biofunctionality. Emulsification and encapsulation of the molecules may improve bioavailability and solubility of thymoquinone. Emulsification systems also face challenges in terms of phase variability and polar instability. In this study, we formulated and characterized submicron oil-in-water (O/W) emulsions encapsulating the black cumin seed oil containing thymoquinone by high-pressure homogenization. We found that the help of identified emulsifying agents can significantly make the delivery system for extracted thymoquinone efficient and stable without any change in the structure or function of the compound. We present the results for interfacial tension, Sauter mean droplet diameter, and zeta potential of the resulting O/W emulsions encapsulating thymoquinone with different emulsifiers and at various pH and temperatures. This novel formulation has potential role in cancer prevention and therapeutics, and could contribute in designing new functional products.

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Identification And Characterization Of *Marsupenaeus Japonicus* Crustin Like Peptide (*Mjcrs*) Isoform From Kuruma Shrimp.

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Antimicrobial peptides (AMP) are an ageless evolutionary growing class of natural and synthetic peptides with a wide spectrum of targets including viruses, bacteria, fungi, and parasites. Till date numerous AMPs have been identified and characterized in crustacean and discovered to exhibit significant variety in their amino acid sequence, structure and biological activity. In the present study, one of the isoform of *Marsupenaeus japonicus* crustin like peptide (*MjCRS* 8) was cloned and confirmed. The tissue distribution analysis revealed its presence mainly from Gill. Sequence data showed 68 % identity with other reported *MjCRS*. Furthermore, phylogenetic analysis confirmed its presence as type II *MjCRS*. These results suggest that there are more types of *MjCRS* isoform exist in *M.japonicus*.

Key words: Antimicrobial peptide, Crustin, Isoform.

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Novel Growth Factor Delivery System for Regenerative Medicine

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Growth factors (GFs) are naturally occurring proteinaceous substances, secreted by surrounding cells essentially required for cellular growth, maturation, proliferation, differentiation and healing of injury. However, we have limited clinical applications due to lack of appropriate delivery systems and biomaterial carriers. Many conventional delivery systems are there to deliver GFs like polymeric particles, emulsions, and dendrimers. In conventional approaches proteins (GFs, enzymes, etc.) undergo several processes and storage-related stresses throughout the life of the product that can result in significant degradation and loss of activity. Usually protein-containing microparticles are prepared by the double emulsion method, such as water/oil/water (W/O/W), solid/oil/water (S/O/W) and water/oil/oil (W/O/O). In the primary emulsion the protein encounters an aqueous-organic interface which causes denaturation of the protein. Added to this are other process-related stresses like high homogenization speed, sonication and temperature. In order to address the aforementioned problems, we have introduced a novel method of protein encapsulation. The Sugar Glass nanoparticle system (SGnPs) is produced by incorporating sugars and other stabilizers along with the proteins in inverse micelles. This will ensure the preservation of activity of the encapsulated protein, by protecting it from the various process-related stresses. Further these SGnPs are used for preparation of polymeric microparticles using the aforementioned conventional methods (W/O/W and W/O/O) for long time storage and control the release pattern. By using of SGnPs for GFs delivery we have achieved 100% encapsulation efficiency and sustained release, only 18% has released in 30 days.

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Central GLP-1 Receptor Agonist Promotes Insulin Release And Lowers Blood Glucose

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Glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonist, liraglutide, is an anti-diabetic drug that lowers blood glucose primarily by stimulating the pancreatic β -cells. In addition, it was reported that peripherally administered liraglutide could access the brain directly. However, its central action to regulate blood glucose is unclear. Here, we investigate the central effect of liraglutide on blood glucose level. Central administration of liraglutide (icv, 3 μ g/3 μ l) in C57B6J mice decreased blood glucose and increased plasma insulin levels without affecting liver glycogen contents and serum corticosterone. Moreover, central administration of liraglutide increased c-Fos immunoreactivity in hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus (PVN) and arcuate nucleus (ARC) and brain stem nucleus tractus solitarius (NTS) and dorsal motor nucleus of the vagus nerve (DMV), and furthermore in POMC neurons in ARC and NTS. The results indicate that liraglutide stimulates the neurocircuit involving the hypothalamus and brain stem, which is relayed to pancreatic β -cells to induce insulin release and thereby lower blood glucose.

Sustainability Of WASHOKU Using DNA Analysis

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“WASHOKU: Traditional Dietary Cultures of the Japan” was registered to the list of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of UNESCO, 2013. WASHOKU preserves the Japanese spirit, ‘respect for nature’. There is a wide variety of regional food culture in the Japanese archipelago spreading from north to south. “Nori” (edible seaweed, (*Pyropia yezoensis*) is cultivated in the seas around Japan, from north to south, and used as a food material such as rice cake, sushi, soba noodle, etc. round the year (Japanese traditional New Year’s morning to New Year’s Eve). “Nori” has remained an essential food composition of WASHOKU. About 1.5 billion pieces and 3.5 billion pieces of “Nori” are exported from China and the Republic of Korea respectively, to all over the world. Nearly two billion pieces of dried lavers are imported from China and the Republic of Korea to Japan, by import quota system.

The purpose of this study is to differentiate the production area of “Nori” by DNA analysis. Japanese Nori (*Pyropia yezoensis* F. *narawaensis*) is genetically homogeneous and different from other *Pyropia* spp. in nucleotide sequences in internal transcribed spacer (ITS)-1 region located between 18S rRNA and 5.8S rRNA. Samples are laver rolled rice cracker, Frikake (sprinkle laver), Onigiri (dried lavers of rice ball) and Kaiten-sushi (sushi served on the conveyor belt). As a result of RFLP analysis, all samples described as domestic production show a fragment of approximately 430 base pair length. Some samples of Kaiten-sushi and soup materials have different fragments of approximately 160 and 280 bp lengths same as in Chinese and Korean samples.

Results from this study will be useful for the conservation of WASHOKU, the domestic farm producers and consumers of “Nori”.

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An Introduction For Shizuoka University's Asia Bridge Program

SHINE Toshihiko

Ph. D. in International Studies (Ethno-history)

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Today Shizuoka, Tomorrow the World- In 2015, Shizuoka University, a Japanese national university in central region, launched a unique industry-academia collaborative program called Asia Bridge Program (ABP). ABP offers a bachelor's program and a master's program for international students from India and other 3 countries (Indonesia, Thailand and Vietnam) to develop academically, professionally, and personally. The ABP bachelor's program (Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Education, Informatics, Science, Engineering and Agriculture) is offered in Japanese, and the master's program (Department of Informatics, Science, Engineering and Agriculture, includes management of business development course, socio- informatics studies courses) is offered in English.

Working closely with Shizuoka-based global corporations such as Suzuki Motor, Yamaha Motor, ABP is designed to educate future global leaders for business and society. The curriculums emphasize a well-rounded interdisciplinary education with a focus on a combination of technical expertise, business sense, scientific thinking, and interpersonal skills through which students grow as liaisons between Shizuoka and their home countries like India.

Tuition Exemption & ABP Scholarship

For your convenience, ABP admissions screening takes place in your countries as well as in Japan, so you do not need to travel for long distance at any point during the application process.

	Application Fee	Enrollment Fee	Tuition	
ABP Program Fee	Waived	Waived	1st year Waived (100%)	2nd-4th year Waived (20% or 100%)
Total Amount	17,000 JPY	202,000 JPY	202,000 JPY / year	

Admissions Screening Process Takes Place Overseas and in Japan

ABP provides all students with financial aid. In addition to exemption from the application and the enrollment fees, it is guaranteed that the first year's tuition is fully waived. Assistance for the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th years will cover 100% of tuition and fees based on an annual assessment of individual academic performance during the previous year (condition: more than 1.5 (GPA)). There is also the ABP monthly stipend for all the first-year students as well as other governmental and corporate-sponsored funding opportunities (40,000 JPY/month for the first 18 months).

October Admissions: ABP is a 4-year program that starts in October with a semester of intensive language training.

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About EcoCycle

We at EcoCycle Corporation are focused on developing cutting-edge technologies for various environmental problems the world is facing today. We have in-house dedicated team of engineers and scientists working on site investigation, soil and groundwater remediation, and water treatment technologies providing one stop solution to the client. We have developed technical partnership with many leading Japanese and American companies specialized in contaminated site investigation and remediation. With the help of inter-disciplinary technical team consisting of hydrogeologists, environmental engineers, chemical engineers, environmental microbiologists, civil engineers and others we can provide tailor-made solutions to the clients worldwide.

- Our Products: Our bioremediation products have been successfully applied for cleaning of over 400 sites contaminated sites with chlorinated hydrocarbons, chromium (VI), petroleum oils and cyanide in Japan, US, Taiwan & other countries.
- Technical capabilities: Knowing the problem as a team, we can successfully implement site-investigation program to understand the extent of contamination, make risk assessment, develop remedial action plan, implement the site cleanup, close the site and deal with the regulating agencies. We do support brownfield site development.
- The solution: Though we are specialized in bioremediation, depending on the problem and available budget, the team is capable of implementing various remediation options such as pump and treat, zero-valent iron treatment, chemical oxidation, soil gas vapor extraction or dig and dispose as lost option.

Some of our Bioremediation

EDC

EDC is wholesome food for specific soil microorganisms. Whereas EDC-E is an emulsified formula designed to release hydrogen over extended period of time and useful for cleaning contaminations of high concentrations in silty or clayey soils. Both the products are diluted in water and injected into subsurface to stimulate native microorganisms in the contaminated site that are capable of degrading chlorinated hydrocarbons.

EDC-E

Target contaminants: Chlorinated hydrocarbons, namely, Tetrachloroethylene, trichloroethylene, trichloroethane, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloroethylenes, dichloroethane, vinyl chloride, chloromethane, chlorobenzenes, etc.

HAR

HAR is a biostimulant for aerobic microorganisms. The product is diluted in oxygen rich water and injected into the contaminated soil and groundwater to stimulate microorganisms that can degrade petroleum hydrocarbons, cyanide compounds, chlorinated hydrocarbons, etc.

Target contaminants: Petroleum hydrocarbons such as Gasoline, diesel, light oil, BTEX, MTBE etc. and Cyanide compounds, dichloroethane, dichloromethane, vinyl chloride, etc.

EcoCycle holds several patents on all the proprietary products and application methods.

In-situ Bioremediation Application Image

Salient Features of our Remediation Products

Low remediation cost, 1/3 of the cost of most of the existing conventional methods, short remediation time, ultra-Low energy requirement and safe, our products are made of food grade materials and are degraded completely.

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